

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for Galectin-1 (P09382) for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

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Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)).

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC005989c006	CVCL_XQ14	HAP1	<i>LGALS1</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the Galectin-1 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab108389**	1018000-29	AB_10863417	recombinant mono	EPR3205	rabbit	1.35	Wb, IF
Abcam	ab138513*	1086382-8	AB_2894851	monoclonal	EPR3206(2)	rabbit	0.26	Wb, IF
Abcam	ab192842**	1011456-2	AB_3725515	recombinant mono	SP247	rabbit	0.04	Wb
ABclonal	A21218**	3522042922	AB_3725523	recombinant mono	ARC53156	rabbit	1.20	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP58491_P050	QC25810-42978	AB_2046045	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	MAB1152*	CJKC0325011	AB_3657585	monoclonal	933133	mouse	0.50	Wb
Cell Signaling Technology	12936**	3	AB_2798065	recombinant mono	D608T	rabbit	0.10	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-32779**	79527780	AB_2810056	recombinant mono	JM13-37	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IP, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-35566**	79531623	AB_2849466	recombinant mono	7W5Q6	rabbit	2.00	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-47904**	79531680	AB_3074348	recombinant mono	SAIC-25B-112	rabbit	1.00	Wb

Wb=western blot; IF= immunofluorescence; IP=immunoprecipitation, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody, NA=not available

A. lysate vs medium

B. screening in lysate

Figure 1: Galectin-1 antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: Galectin-1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 3: Galectin-1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: Galectin-1 antibody screening by western blot.

A) 10 µg of lysate and culture medium from HAP1 WT and *LGALS1* KO were processed for western blot with the Galectin-1 antibody 12936** diluted at 1/1000. **B)** 20 µg of lysate from HAP1 WT and *LGALS1* KO were processed for western blot with the indicated Galectin-1 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab108389** at 1/100, ab138513* at 1/10 000, ab192842** at 1/100, A21218** at 1/11 000, ARP58491_P050 at 1/100, MAB1152* at 1/250, 12936** at 1/1000, MA5-32779** at 1/2000, MA5-35566** at 1/200, MA5-47904** at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 14.7 kDa. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: Galectin-1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

HAP1 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed for 2 h using 0.2 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated Galectin-1 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the Galectin-1 antibody A21218** used at 1/3000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 3: Galectin-1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

HAP1 WT and *LGALS1* KO cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio in a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom. Cells were stained with the indicated Galectin-1 antibodies and with the corresponding fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (WT), red (antibody staining) and far-red (KO) channels was performed. Representative images of the blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. When an antibody was recommended for immunofluorescence by the supplier, we tested it at the recommended dilution. The rest of the antibodies were tested at 1 and 2 µg/ml, and the final concentration was selected based on the detection range of the microscope used and a quantitative analysis not shown here. Antibody dilutions used: ab108389** at 1/100, ab138513* at 1/250, ab192842** at 1/100, A21218** at 1/500, ARP58491_P050 at 1/250, MAB1152* at 1/500, 12936** at 1/50, MA5-32779** at 1/2000, MA5-35566** at 1/100, MA5-47904** at 1/1000. Bars = 10 µm. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.